

Short Baseline Neutrino Anomalies: *Evolving Perspectives on an Enduring Puzzle*

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COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY
IN THE CITY OF NEW YORK

The Short Baseline Anomalies

The LSND Anomaly

LSND used a beam of $\bar{\nu}_\mu$, from **muon decay-at-rest**, to search for $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$ appearance oscillations

Observed a **3.8 σ** significance excess

Background ν_e contamination was at the level of **0.078%**

The MiniBooNE Anomaly

MiniBooNE was an 800 ton Cherenkov detector

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ appearance oscillations using neutrinos from meson decay-in-flight at the Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB) at Fermilab

Observed a 4.8σ significance excess

The Gallium Anomaly

Looking for neutrinos from radioactive ^{51}Cr and ^{37}Ar sources in two experiments **SAGE** and **GALLEX** circa 1999.

Sensitive to $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$ disappearance oscillations

Observed a $\sim 2.5\sigma$ significance deficit

Gallium Anomaly
Radioactive Source

The Gallium Anomaly

Looking for neutrinos from radioactive ^{51}Cr and ^{37}Ar sources in two experiments **SAGE** and **GALLEX** circa 1999.

Recently replicated by the **BEST** experiment
([PhysRevLett.128.232501](https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01232) (2022))

Sensitive to $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$ disappearance
oscillations

Observed a $\sim 4.0\sigma$
significance deficit

The Short-Baseline Anomalies

The Short-Baseline Anomalies, discovery of a New Neutrino?

All *individually* consistent with neutrino oscillations with a mass difference $\Delta m^2 \sim \mathcal{O}(1 \text{ eV}^2)$

LSND Anomaly
Decay-at-rest

$\sim 3.8\sigma$

MiniBooNE Anomaly
Decay-in-flight

$\sim 4.8\sigma$

Gallium Anomaly
Radioactive Source

$\sim 4.0\sigma$

A Sterile Neutrino?

Mass difference $\Delta m^2 \sim O(1 \text{ eV}^2)$

This does **not line up** with the global "**3 neutrino paradigm**" picture

A Sterile Neutrino?

Mass difference $\Delta m^2 \sim \mathcal{O}(1 \text{ eV}^2)$

This does **not line up** with the global "**3 neutrino paradigm**" picture and LEP electroweak precision data

$$\Delta m^2 \approx 1 \text{ eV}^2$$

ν_4

Need a 4th "sterile" neutrino

ν_3

3 Neutrino Paradigm

$$\Delta m_{31}^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$$

ν_2

$$\Delta m_{21}^2 = 7.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$$

ν_1

Multiple independent anomalous μ signals consistent with a 4th eV scale neutrino..
 Why is there still debate? Where's the ?

~3.8 σ

LSND Anomaly
 Decay-at-rest

~4.8 σ

MiniBooNE Anomaly
 Decay-in-flight

~4.0 σ

Gallium Anomaly
 Radioactive Source

The Short-Baseline Anomalies, discovery of a Sterile Neutrino?

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Gallium Anomaly
Radioactive Source

$\sim 4.0\sigma$

Where do we stand,
globally, on sterile
neutrinos?

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ **Positive Hints**

- LSND
- MiniBooNE

 $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$ **Positive Hints**

- Gallium

Positive Hints

- LSND
- MiniBooNE

Null Results

- KARMEN
- CCFR
- NuTeV
- NOMAD

- **CCFR [1984] @ Fermilab**
 - PhysRevLett.52:10.1103, 1984
- **KARMEN [2002] @ RAL (UK)**
 - Phys.Rev.D65:112001,2002
- **NuTeV [2002] @ Fermilab**
 - Phys.Rev.Lett.89:011804,2002
- **NOMAD [2003] @ CERN**
 - Phys.Lett.B570:19-31,2003

Positive Hints

- LSND
- MiniBooNE

Null Results

- KARMEN
- CCFR
- NuTeV
- NOMAD
- OPERA
- MicroBooNE

- **OPERA [2019] @ Gran Sasso**

- Phys. Rev. D 100, 051301 (2019)
- Very long baseline, 730 km, oscillations average out for LSND/MiniBooNE regions

- **MicroBooNE [2023] @ Fermilab**

- Phys. Rev. Lett. 130, 011801 (2023)
- Same beamline as MiniBooNE!

Mild deficit
observed
actually

As of **2024**, pesky region unprobed..

Positive Hints

- LSND
- MiniBooNE

Null Results

- KARMEN
- CCFR
- NuTeV
- NOMAD
- OPERA
- MicroBooNE

The Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB)

Fermilab

Protons

470m

500m

The Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB)

Fermilab

Protons

Booster
Accelerator
~8 GeV

Be

π^+
 K^+
 π^-

Total ν_e
observed

$N\nu_e$

Total ν_e
observed

$N\nu_\mu \times P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e)$

$N\nu_e \times P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e)$

$$\frac{N\nu_\mu}{N\nu_e} = \frac{\sin^2 2\theta_{ee}}{\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu e}}$$

Cancelation/
Degeneracy
when equal

Given fixed content of your neutrino beam, there will be places where appearance and disappearance cancel.

The Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB)

Fermilab

Protons

Booster
Accelerator
~8 GeV

$$\frac{N\nu_\mu}{N\nu_e} \sim 200$$

Be

π^+
 K^+
 π^-

The Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB)

Degeneracy
weakening the result

$$\frac{N\nu_\mu}{N\nu_e} \sim 200$$

Prediction at MicroBooNE (BNB)

Both Red and Blue curves have **same** $\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu e}$

In Red, however, the appearance and disappearance degeneracy cancels such that it appears like no oscillations

Somewhat unavoidable! $\frac{N\nu_{\mu}}{N\nu_e} \sim 200$
 Down to the beam content!

The NuMI Neutrino Beam

Fermilab

Protons

Booster
Accelerator
~8 GeV

Be

π^+
 K^+
 π^-

Main Injector
~120 GeV
Protons

8.0° off-axis

π^+ K^+ π^-

The NuMI Neutrino Beam

Fermilab

Protons

Booster
Accelerator
~8 GeV

Be

π^+
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The NuMI Neutrino Beam

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$$\frac{N\nu_\mu}{N\nu_e} \sim 200$$

$$\frac{N\nu_\mu}{N\nu_e} \sim 24$$

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Prediction at MicroBooNE (BNB)

$$\frac{N\nu_\mu}{N\nu_e} \sim 24$$

Prediction at MicroBooNE (NuMI)

NuMI breaks degeneracy by probing oscillations using very different beam

BNB

ν_e CC FC MicroBooNE BNB 6.369×10^{20} POT

BNB

NuMI

MicroBooNE 95% CL result

- Excludes entire LSND 99% allowed region
- Excludes vast majority of MiniBooNE 95% allowed region

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- MiniBooNE

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ν_e Disappearance

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$

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$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium

Null Results

$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

Three strategies to see short-baseline reactor oscillations:

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium

Null Results

$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

Three strategies to see short-baseline reactor oscillations:

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

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$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

Three strategies to see short-baseline reactor oscillations:

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$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

Three strategies to see short-baseline reactor oscillations:

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium

Null Results

$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

- Commercial reactor, 100 MW_{th} in Russia

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints Null Results

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4?

Neutrino-4 Positive Signal?

Best-Fit oscillation
 $\Delta m^2 = 7.3 \text{ eV}^2$, $\sin^2 2\theta = 0.36$ @ **2.9 σ** significance

Several questions have been raised by community so far, including the **effects of the statistical approach used**, and impact of **systematics** and **expected backgrounds**

- H. Almazán et al, [arXiv:2006.13147](https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.13147)
- C. Giunti et al [j.physletb.2021.136214](https://arxiv.org/abs/2021.136214)

“Therefore, we conclude that the claimed Neutrino-4 indication in favor of short-baseline neutrino oscillations with very large mixing is rather doubtful.”

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- **Neutrino 4?**

Null Results

$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

DANSS, Movable detector in Russia,
Phys.Lett.B 787(2018)56-63

NEOS+RENO, relative 419 m RENO and 24m
 NEOS detectors in Korea
Phys. Rev. D 105, L111101 (2022)

Need to get closer to reactors!

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

Null Results

- DANSS
- NEOS+RENO

$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

STEREO (ILL, Grenoble, France)

- [Nature 613, 257–261 \(2023\)](#)
- **9.4 to 11.1 m Baselines**

PROSPECT (Oak Ridge National Lab, USA)

- [arXiv:2406.10408 \[hep-ex\] \(2024\)](#)
- **7-9 m Baselines**

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

Null Results

- DANSS
- NEOS+RENO
- STEREO
- PROSPECT-I

ν_e Disappearance

KATRIN in Karlsruhe Germany

Designed to determine the **neutrino mass** from kinematic measurements of the **β -decay of tritium**

PhysRevD.105.072004 (2022)

Unique! KATRIN is a **non-oscillatory** lab experiment sensitive to relevant solutions at large Δm^2 values!

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

Null Results

- DANSS
- NEOS+RENO
- STEREO
- PROSPECT-I
- KATRIN

As of **2024**, pesky “Gap”
region unprobed..

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

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Analyzed **36 million tritium β -decay electrons** in a data set taken over **259 days**

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- **A sixfold increase in statistics** over 2022 results
- **Substantial improvements** understanding of **systematics**.

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

Null Results

- DANSS
- NEOS+RENO
- STEREO
- PROSPECT-I
- KATRIN

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

Null Results

- DANSS
- NEOS+RENO
- STEREO
- PROSPECT-I
- KATRIN (2025)

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$

As of the start of **2025**,
pesky "**Gap**" regions
unprobed..

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$

2025 has been an impressive year for advancing our understanding of light sterile neutrinos!

Article

Search for light sterile neutrinos with two neutrino beams at MicroBooNE

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09757-7>The MicroBooNE Collaboration¹⁰

Received: 19 December 2024

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Published online: 3 December 2025

Open access

 Check for updates

The existence of three distinct neutrino flavours, ν_e , ν_μ , and ν_τ , is a central tenet of the Standard Model of particle physics^{1,2}. Quantum-mechanical interference can allow a neutrino of one initial flavour to be detected sometime later as a different flavour, a process called neutrino oscillation. Several anomalous observations inconsistent with this three-flavour picture have motivated the hypothesis that an additional neutrino state exists, which does not interact directly with matter, termed as 'sterile' neutrino, ν_s (refs. 3–9). This includes anomalous observations from the Liquid Scintillator Neutrino Detector (LSND)³ experiment and Mini-Booster Neutrino Experiment (MiniBooNE)^{4,5}, consistent with $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_s$ transitions at a distance inconsistent with the three-neutrino picture. Here we use data obtained from the MicroBooNE liquid-argon time projection chamber¹⁰ in two accelerator neutrino beams to exclude the single light sterile neutrino interpretation of the LSND and MiniBooNE anomalies at the 95% confidence level (CL). Moreover, we rule out a notable portion of the parameter space that could explain the gallium anomaly^{6–8}. This is one of the first measurements to use two accelerator neutrino beams to break a degeneracy between ν_s appearance and disappearance, which would otherwise weaken the sensitivity to the sterile neutrino hypothesis. We find no evidence for either $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_s$ flavour transitions or ν_s disappearance that would indicate non-standard flavour oscillations. Our results indicate that previous anomalous observations consistent with $\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_s$ transitions cannot be explained by introducing a single sterile neutrino state.

Article

Sterile-neutrino search based on 259 days of KATRIN data

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09739-9>The KATRIN Collaboration¹

Received: 2 April 2025

Accepted: 9 October 2025

Published online: 3 December 2025

Open access

 Check for updates

Neutrinos are the most abundant fundamental matter particles in the Universe and play a crucial part in particle physics and cosmology. Neutrino oscillation, discovered about 25 years ago, shows that the three known species mix with each other. Anomalous results from reactor and radioactive-source experiments¹ suggest a possible fourth neutrino state, the sterile neutrino, which does not interact through the weak force. The Karlsruhe Tritium Neutrino (KATRIN) experiment², primarily designed to measure the neutrino mass using tritium β -decay, also searches for sterile neutrinos suggested by these anomalies. A sterile-neutrino signal would appear as a distortion in the β -decay energy spectrum, characterized by a discontinuity in curvature (kink) related to the sterile-neutrino mass. This signature, which depends only on the shape of the spectrum rather than its absolute normalization, offers a robust, complementary approach to reactor experiments. Here we report the analysis of the energy spectrum of 36 million tritium β -decay electrons recorded in 259 measurement days within the last 40 eV below the endpoint. The results exclude a substantial part of the parameter space suggested by the gallium anomaly and challenge the Neutrino-4 claim. Together with other neutrino-disappearance experiments, KATRIN probes sterile-to-active mass splittings from a fraction of an eV² to several hundred eV², excluding light sterile neutrinos with mixing angles above a few per cent.

NEWS AND VIEWS | 03 December 2025

Still no sign of hypothetical sterile-neutrino particle

A particle called the sterile neutrino could explain anomalies in high-energy physics.

The range of conditions in which it could be found has become narrower.

By [Patrick Huber](#)

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) \simeq 4|U_{\mu 4}|^2 \boxed{|U_{e 4}|^2} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E_\nu} \right)$$

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) \simeq \boxed{1 - 4|U_{e 4}|^2(1 - |U_{e 4}|^2)} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{14}^2 L}{4E_\nu} \right)$$

$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$

$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) \simeq 4 |U_{\mu 4}|^2 |U_{e 4}|^2 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E_\nu} \right)$$

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) \simeq [1 - 4 |U_{e 4}|^2 (1 - |U_{e 4}|^2)] \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{14}^2 L}{4E_\nu} \right)$$

$$P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu) \simeq [1 - 4 |U_{\mu 4}|^2 (1 - |U_{\mu 4}|^2)] \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E_\nu} \right)$$

ν_μ Disappearance

- **CCFR [1984] @ Fermilab**
 - [PhysRevLett.52.10.1103, 1984](#)
- **CDHS [1984] @ CERN**
 - [PhysRevLett.52.10.1103, 1984](#)
- **MiniBooNE & SciBooNE [2011] @ Fermilab**
 - [Phys. Rev. D 85, 032007 \(2012\)](#)

Positive Hints

Null Results

- CCFR
- CDHS
- MiniBooNE

ν_μ Disappearance

- **Super-Kamiokande**
 - [Phys. Rev. D 91, 052019](#)
- **T2K [2019]**
 - [Phys. Rev. D 99, 071103](#)
- **NOvA [2024]**
 - [arXiv 2409.04553](#)
- **MINOS/MINOS+**
 - [Phys. Rev. Lett. 122, 091803](#)

"No muon disappearance ever observed from huge variety of experiments! Contradiction to MiniBooNE & LSND!"

Me, 2024

Positive Hints

Null Results

- CCFR
- CDHS
- MiniBooNE
- Super-K
- T2K
- NOvA
- MINOS

Latest IceCube atmospheric result has closed contour at the 95% C.L. [arXiv:2405.08070 \[hep-ex\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.08070)

*"This probability, corresponding to a significance of **2.2 σ** , does **not constitute evidence** for the existence of an eV scale sterile neutrino."*

... But it is the first ever **hint** in the muon sector

“This probability, corresponding to a significance of **2.2 σ** , does **not constitute evidence** for the existence of an eV scale sterile neutrino.”

... But it is the first ever **hint** in the muon sector

$$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$$

Positive Hints

- IceCube

Null Results

- CCFR
- CDHS
- MiniBooNE
- Super-K
- T2K
- NOvA
- MINOS

Where we Stand?

Positive Hints

- LSND
- MiniBooNE

Null Results

- Karmen
- NuTeV
- CCFR
- NOMAD
- OPERA
- MicroBooNE

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino-4

Null Results

- NEOS+RENO
- DANSS
- PROSPECT
- STEREO
- KATRIN

Positive Hints

- IceCube

Null Results

- MiniBooNE
- CDHS
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- T2K
- NoVA
- MINOS
- Super-K

The Elephant in the Room...

HUGE tension
between
cosmological
bounds and *vanilla*
**3+1 short-baseline
steriles**

S. Hagstotz et al, [PhysRevD.104.123524](https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.08757)

HUGE tension
between
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bounds and **vanilla**
**3+1 short-baseline
steriles**

Energy density of **Relativistic Neutrinos**

S. Hagstotz et al, [PhysRevD.104.123524](https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.07412)

$$N_{\text{eff}}^{\nu} = \frac{8}{7} \left(\frac{11}{4} \right)^{4/3} \frac{\rho_{\nu}}{\rho_{\gamma}}$$

$$N_{\text{eff}} = 2.99 \pm 0.17 \text{ (CMB+lens+BAO) } \text{ [Plank2018](#) }$$

**Can this be avoided? Is this
dependent on specific models
of Λ CDM?**

**Possibly, but you have to add
more new physics! It's no longer a
simple vanilla "3+1" model**

Where We Stand – 2026

- There has been **EXTREME tension** in global data for a “light 3+1 oscillating sterile neutrinos” for years, gets *much worse* with **cosmology** included

Where We Stand – 2026

- There has been **EXTREME tension** in global data for a “light 3+1 oscillating sterile neutrinos” for years, gets *much worse* with **cosmology** included
- **Not just “global” tension anymore**, with new **results in 2025** directly ruling out almost the entire viable parameter space of various anomalies
 - The proverbial “**nail-in-the-coffin**” for **eV² scale sterile neutrino** solutions of the Short-Baseline Anomalies?

If a model fails to explain the data *throw out the model, not the data.*

If not eV^2 scale sterile neutrinos, then what?

LSND Anomaly

Decay-at-rest

$\sim 3.8\sigma$

MiniBooNE Anomaly

Decay-in-flight

$\sim 4.8\sigma$

Gallium Anomaly

Radioactive Source

$\sim 4.0\sigma$

Additions/Modifications to light sterile neutrino oscillations* I.e 3+1 + something else

- **3+2** and **3+3** (more light steriles)
 - C. Giunti *et al* Phys.Rev.D 84 (2011) 9, 073008
- **3+1+Non-Standard interactions** (NSI)
 - J. Liao *et al* Phys.Rev.D 99 (2019) 1, 015016
- **3+1+Decay**
 - Z.Moss *et al* Phys.Rev.D 97, (2018) 055017
- **3+1+Decoherence**
 - C.A. Argüelles *et al* C.Phys. Rev. D 107 (2023), 036004
- **3+1+Resonance Matter Effects**
 - D.Alves *et al* JHEP08 (2022) 034

Lots of effort in this direction, to **keep the core 3+1 light oscillating sterile neutrino model** and modify slightly to **help reduce tension**

Sub percent level effects

20% disappearance effect! HUGE

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- JSNS² provides a **direct test** of LSND
- Uses the **same neutrino source** (muon decay-at-rest) and **same detection principle** (Inverse-beta-decay) as LSND.

1st Phase: JSNS² [\[1310.1347\]](#)

- Single Detector. Commissioned 2020,
- Physics run 2021-2024 with 4.85×10^{22} POT collected [\[2412.18509\]](#)
- **Preparing to unblind the signal region for 2022 data**

2nd Phase: JSNS²-II [\[2012.10807\]](#)

Upgrade to **two detectors**, Second, far detector commissioned, awaiting beam

- Near@24m (17 tons, 120 10" PMTs)
- Far @ 28m (32 tons, 220 10" PMTs)

LSND Anomaly

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Gallium Anomaly

Radioactive Source

$\sim 4.0\sigma$

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The Gallium Anomaly

- BEST **was** the new testing ground for this decades old anomaly
- BEST result is **extremely compelling**, the **anomaly is confirmed** but sterile origin is NOT confirmed

BEST designed as a two-distance oscillation experiment from the start **Inner** and **Outer** volumes

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Protons

500m

MiniBooNE and the SBN Program

Protons

110 ton

110m

90 ton

470m

476 ton

600m

500m

Electrons ..

MiniBooNE couldn't separate
electrons...

Electron cherenkov
ring event

Electrons or Photons ..

Electron cherenkov ring event

Electrons or Photons ..

“But they were, all of them,
deceived, for another
Cherenkov Ring was made...”

MiniBooNE couldn't separate
electrons from **photons**

Electrons or Photons or e^+e^- pairs!

“But they were, all of them, deceived, for another Cherenkov Ring was made...”

MiniBooNE couldn't separate electrons from photons or from electron-positron pairs

Beyond vanilla sterile neutrino explanations of the MiniBooNE Anomaly

Category	Model	Signature	Anomalie		References
			LSND	MiniBooNE	
Flavor transitions Secs. 3.1.1-3.1.3, 3.1.5	(3+1) oscillations		✓	✓	Reviews and global fits [93, 103, 105, 106]
	oscillations				

Vanilla “3+1” not viable

 Electron signals

Table modified from Snowmass [White Paper](#) on Light Sterile Neutrino Searches and Related Phenomenology

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	(3+1) w/ invisible sterile decay	oscillations w/ ν_4 invisible decay	✓	✓	[151, 155]
	(3+1) w/ sterile decay	$\nu_4 \rightarrow \phi \nu_e$	✓	✓	[159–162, 270]
Matter effects Secs. 3.1.4, 3.1.7	(3+1) w/ anomalous matter effects	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ via matter effects	✓	✓	[143, 147, 271–273]
	(3+1) w/ quasi-sterile neutrinos	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ w/ resonant ν_s matter effects	✓	✓	[148]

“3+1” Extensions. Needs to be conclusively studied, but difficult

 Electron signals

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Flavor transitions Secs. 3.1.1-3.1.3, 3.1.5	(3+1) oscillations	ν_e oscillations	✓	✓	Reviews and global fits [93, 103, 105, 106]
	(3+1) w/ invisible sterile decay	oscillations w/ ν_4 invisible decay	✓	✓	[151, 155]
	(3+1) w/ sterile decay	$\nu_4 \rightarrow \phi \nu_e$	✓	✓	[159–162, 270]
Matter effects Secs. 3.1.4, 3.1.7	(3+1) w/ anomalous matter effects	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ via matter effects	✓	✓	[143, 147, 271–273]
	(3+1) w/ quasi-sterile neutrinos	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ w/ resonant ν_s matter effects	✓	✓	[148]
Flavor violation Sec. 3.1.6	Lepton-flavor-violating μ decays	$\mu \rightarrow e \nu_\alpha \nu_e$	✓	✗	[174, 175, 274]
	neutrino-flavor-changing bremsstrahlung	$\nu_\mu A \rightarrow \nu_e A$	✓	✓	[275]
Decays in flight Sec. 3.2.3	Transition magnetic mom., heavy ν decay	$N \rightarrow \nu \gamma$	✗	✓	[207]
	Dark sector heavy neutrino decay	$\nu(X) \rightarrow \nu \gamma$	✗	✓	[208]
Neutrino Scattering Secs. 3.2.1, 3.2.2	neutrino-induced upscattering	$\nu \rightarrow \nu e^+ e^-$ $N \rightarrow \nu e^+ e^-$	✓	✓	[205, 206, 209–216]
	neutrino dipole upscattering	$\nu \rightarrow \nu e^+ e^-$	✓	✓	[40, 185, 187, 188, 190, 193, 233, 276]
Dark Matter Scattering Sec. 3.2.4	dark particle-induced upscattering	$e^- e^- \rightarrow e^- e^-$	✗	✓	[217]
	dark particle-induced inverse Primakoff	γ	✓	✓	[217]

- Electron signals
- Photon signals
- Di-Photon signals
- e+e- signals

30+ dark-sector models in last few years with Incredibly rich and varied phenomenology

Table modified from Snowmass [White Paper](#) on Light Sterile Neutrino Searches and Related Phenomenology

Beyond vanilla sterile neutrino explanations of the MiniBooNE Anomaly

Category	Model	Signature	Anomalie		References
			LSND	MiniBooNE	
Flavor transitions Secs. 3.1.1-3.1.3, 3.1.5	(3+1) oscillations	oscillations	✓	✓	Reviews and global fits [93, 103, 105, 106]
	(3+1) w/ invisible sterile decay	oscillations w/ ν_4 invisible decay	✓	✓	[151, 155]
	(3+1) w/ sterile decay	$\nu_4 \rightarrow \phi \nu_e$	✓	✓	[159–162, 270]
Matter effects Secs. 3.1.4, 3.1.7	(3+1) w/ anomalous matter effects	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ via matter effects	✓	✓	[143, 147, 271–273]
	(3+1) w/ quasi-sterile neutrinos	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ w/ resonant ν_s matter effects	✓	✓	[148]
Flavor violation Sec. 3.1.6	Lepton-flavor-violating μ decays	$\mu \rightarrow e \nu_\alpha \nu_e$	✓	✗	[174, 175, 274]
	neutrino-flavor-changing bremsstrahlung	$\nu_\mu A \rightarrow \nu_e A$	✓	✓	[275]
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Dark Matter Scattering Sec. 3.2.4	dark particle-induced upscattering	$\nu \rightarrow \nu e^+ e^-$	✗	✓	[217]
	dark particle-induced inverse Primakoff	$\nu \rightarrow \nu e^+ e^-$	✓	✓	[217]

- Electron signals
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30+ dark-sector models in last few years with Incredibly rich and varied phenomenology

Table modified from Snowmass [White Paper](#) on Light Sterile Neutrino Searches and Related Phenomenology

E.g Neutrino induced upscattering

Neutrino induced upscattering to produce a heavy **dark neutrino ν_4** via a new **dark gauge boson Z'**

ν_4 unstable !

Decays $\nu_4 \rightarrow \nu_\alpha e^+e^-$

E. Bertuzzo et al Phys. Rev. Lett. 121, 241801
P.Ballet et al. Phys. Rev. D 99, 071701

M. Ross-Lonergan - Jan 7th - NuPhys 2026

MiniBooNE

Protons

Booster Accelerator
~8 GeV

Be

π^+
 π^-
 K^+

110 ton

110m

90 ton

470m

476 ton

600m

The SBN program at Fermilab is the **ideal place** to probe these **BSM photon and e+e- dark sector models** that could be solutions of the MiniBooNE Anomaly

MicroBooNE targets MiniBooNE Anomaly

 Fermilab

Protons

Booster
Accelerator
~8 GeV

90 ton

470m

Be

π^+
 K^+
 π^-

Suite of Photon/ e^+e^- Results from MicroBooNE

Search for Neutrino-Induced Neutral-Current Δ **Radiative Decay** in MicroBooNE and a First Test of the MiniBooNE Low Energy Excess

- [arXiv:2502.05750 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.05750)

Enhanced Search for Neutral Current Δ **Radiative** Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.05750 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.05750)

First Search for Neutral Current **Coherent** Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.06091 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06091)

Inclusive Search for Anomalous Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.06064 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06064)

First Search for **Dark Sector e^+e^-** Explanations of the MiniBooNE Anomaly at MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.10900 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.10900)

Two key facts to understand photon/ e^+e^- searches

Two key facts to understand photon/e+e- searches

1. π^0 's are the dominant, and often irreducible, background

Two key facts to understand photon/e+e- searches

1. π^0 's are the dominant, and often irreducible, background

True Single Photon

Near *Irreducible* Background
Looks like a Single Photon

Two key facts to understand photon/ e^+e^- searches

1. π^0 's are the dominant, and often irreducible, background
2. **Broadly speaking two categories of searches, photons with and without hadronic/proton activity**

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Photon + Protons

Photon + No Protons

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1. π^0 's are the dominant, and often irreducible, background
2. **Broadly speaking two categories of searches, photons with and without hadronic/proton activity**

Photon + Protons

Photon + No Protons

Single-Photon with Protons

Enhanced Search for Neutral Current Δ Radiative
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

○ [arXiv:2502.05750 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.05750)

Inclusive Search for Anomalous
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

○ [arXiv:2502.06064 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06064)

Enhanced Search for Neutral Current Δ Radiative Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

○ [arXiv:2502.05750 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.05750)

Inclusive Search for Anomalous Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

○ [arXiv:2502.06064 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06064)

- In all cases, consistent picture, good agreement with predictions
 - **No Anomalous Excess**
- Backgrounds ~70→80% NC π^0 but we would expect to be sensitive to a MiniBooNE size signal,

Two key facts to understand photon/ e^+e^- searches

1. π^0 's are dominant, and often irreducible, background
2. **Broadly speaking two categories of searches, photons with and without hadronic/proton activity**

Photon + Protons

Photon + No Protons

Single-Photon **without** Protons

Enhanced Search for Neutral Current Δ Rad
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

○ [arXiv:2502.05750 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.05750)

First Search for Neutral Current **Coh**
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

○ [arXiv:2502.06091 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06091)

- *Broadly* good agreement with predictions...
- A few local bumps ~insignificant, and crucially **none of them were particularly sensitive!** NC π^0 backgrounds much harder with no vertex!

Single-Photon **without** Protons

Enhanced Search for Neutral Current **Δ Rad**
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.05750 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.05750)

First Search for Neutral Current **Coh**
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.06091 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06091)

Inclusive Search for Anomalous
Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE

- [arXiv:2502.06064 \[hep-ex\] \(2025\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06064)

Excess of **$93 \pm 22(\text{stat.}) \pm 35(\text{syst.})$**
data events (**2.2σ**) from 0-600 MeV

- *Broadly* good agreement with predictions...
- A few local bumps ~insignificant, and crucially **none of them were particularly sensitive!** NC π^0 backgrounds much harder with no vertex!
- The one analysis that *is more sensitive*, the inclusive analysis, sees a mild **2.2σ** excess, contained below 600 MeV

Overall Kinematic Agreement

MiniBoONE

Shower/Visible Energy

Excess

Shower/Visible Angle

MicroBoONE

Shower Energy vs Angle - Excess Events

First search target a specific class of
Dark Neutrino Upscattering models

E. Bertuzzo et al Phys. Rev. Lett. 121, 241801

P.Ballet et al. Phys. Rev. D 99, 071701

Bkg Prediction : 69.7 ± 17.3 events

Observed Data : **95** events

First search target a specific class of **Dark Neutrino Upscattering** models

E. Bertuzzo et al Phys. Rev. Lett. 121, 241801

P.Ballet et al. Phys. Rev. D 99, 071701

The **world's first direct limits** on these dark sector models and, at the 95% confidence level, **excludes the majority of the parameter space viable as a solution to the MiniBooNE anomaly**

Bkg Prediction : **69.7 ± 17.3** events

Observed Data : **95** events

Origin of MiniBooNE Anomaly : MicroBooNE's Scoresheet

	Protons	Zero Proton

- 3+1 sterile neutrino model no longer a viable solution
- **But anomalies still need explanation!**

Photon/ e^+e^-
Boundary
not clear

Origin of MiniBooNE Anomaly : MicroBooNE's Scoresheet

	Protons	Zero Proton
Photon/ e^+e^- Boundary not clear		

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- **Tantalizing hint** consistent with MiniBooNE observed in 1γ zero proton
- The last remaining place a SM explanation **could** hide

Origin of MiniBooNE Anomaly : MicroBooNE's Scoresheet

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- **But anomalies still need explanation!**
- **Tantalizing hint** consistent with MiniBooNE observed in 1y zero proton
- The last remaining place a SM explanation **could** hide
- MicroBooNE has completed **first search for Dark Sector e^+e^- solutions**
- No signal observed, but **necessarily model dependent**
- Proof that LArTPC's can probe this sector, **open the door for more to come!**

**Towards
Definitive
Resolution**

What's Next?

Fermilab

Protons

Booster
Accelerator
~8 GeV

Be

π^+
 K^+
 π^-

110 ton

110m

90 ton

470m

476 ton

600m

Search Continues at MicroBooNE!

- Double the data collected
- Extremely well understood detector
- Improved reconstruction

If the **2.2 σ hint is real**, and anomaly is single-photon no proton, MicroBooNE should be able to confirm it!

Fermilab

Protons

Booster Accelerator
~8 GeV

110 ton

90 ton

μBooNE

476 ton

110m

470m

600m

SBND

Search Continues at MicroBooNE!

- Double the data collected
- Extremely well understood detector
- Improved reconstruction

A lot of dark sector physics is not oscillatory

$$\propto \frac{1}{R^2}$$

$$\frac{L_{\mu B}^2}{L_{SBND}^2} \frac{M_{SBND}}{M_{\mu B}} \approx \frac{470^2}{110^2} \frac{110}{90} \approx \boxed{\times 22}$$

Huge Rate increase moving to SBND

If the **2.2σ** hint is real, and anomaly is single-photon no proton, MicroBooNE should be able to confirm it!

3+ million neutrino interactions already!
MicroBooNE had $O(500k)$ in 5 years

By 2027 will have **10 million neutrino interactions**

- *1-in-3 of ALL neutrinos observed by human-kind will be in SBND!*

Run 1: December 2024 → June 2025

Run 2: Started October 15th 2025

See talk by Rachel Coackley Tomorrow!

Protons

Booster Accelerator
~8 GeV

Be

π^+
 π^-
 K^+

110 ton

110m

μ BooNE

470m

476 ton

600m

- **3+2** and **3+3** (more light steriles)
 - C. Giunti *et al* Phys.Rev.D 84 (2011) 9, 073008
- **3+1+Non-Standard interactions** (NSI)
 - J. Liao *et al* Phys.Rev.D 99 (2019) 1, 015016
- **3+1+Decay**
 - Z.Moss *et al* Phys.Rev.D 97, (2018) 055017
- **3+1+Decoherence**
 - C.A. Argüelles *et al* C.Phys. Rev. D 107 (2023), 036004
- **3+1+Resonance Matter Effects**
 - D.Alves *et al* JHEP08 (2022) 034

To **definitively** answer **all questions** in regards 3+1 and all extended models of light oscillating neutrinos, the full SBN program including **SBND (near)** and **ICARUS (far)** detector will be unparalleled.

ICARUS has been taking data since 2021

First Search for Sterile Neutrino Oscillation Leading to ν_μ Disappearance in the Booster Neutrino Beam at ICARUS

Fermilab Wine and Cheese Seminar by
Elizabeth Worchester on behalf of **ICARUS**

<https://indico.fnal.gov/event/71402/>

Abstract: The ICARUS Collaboration operated the 760-ton T600 detector in a successful three-year physics run at the underground LNGS laboratory, carrying out a sensitive search for LSND-like anomalous appearance in the CERN Neutrinos to Gran Sasso beam. Following a major overhaul at CERN, the ICARUS T600 detector was installed at Fermilab and began operations in 2020, recording its first neutrino events from the Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB) and from the off-axis Neutrinos at the Main Injector (NuMI) beam. In late 2025, ICARUS celebrated five continuous years of data taking, marking an important milestone for large-scale LAr-TPC technology as it advances neutrino physics and supports future projects such as DUNE.

In this seminar, the first search for muon-neutrino disappearance in the BNB using the ICARUS detector is presented. Neutrino events, identified as charged-current muon-neutrino interactions with a final state consisting of a muon and at least one proton ($1\mu Np$), are selected from data collected during 2022–2023 (ICARUS Run 2) and compared with simulation-based expectations. For the first time, results are interpreted within a two-neutrino approximation of the sterile $3+1$ model, including the effects of systematic uncertainties arising from flux, neutrino-interaction, and detector modeling.

Although limited by systematic uncertainties—dominated by currently unconstrained flux and interaction models—this first ICARUS oscillation analysis allows the investigation of the region of oscillation parameter space indicated by current muon-neutrino disappearance experiments. Furthermore, it paves the way for future SBN analyses, in which combined data from SBND and ICARUS will significantly constrain these uncertainties and definitively address the long-standing sterile-neutrino anomalies.

Dear Colleagues,

We are organizing a **Mini-Workshop on Short Baseline Neutrino Anomalies** on **Jan 16th, 2026**, as part of the Neutrino Physics Center (NPC) at Fermilab.

This will be a **one-morning, hybrid workshop**, running from 8:00-11:00 am Fermilab time. The program will feature a theory overview, followed by experimental talks on **recent sterile neutrino oscillation results** from **KATRIN, MicroBoONE and ICARUS** experiments, and will conclude with a **panel discussion**.

Additional details including the full agenda, speaker and panelist names, and the zoom connection will be shared after the holidays.

The workshop is open to the broader worldwide neutrino community, and we warmly invite you to join us, hear about the latest results, and take part in the discussion. You are welcome to join either in person at Fermilab or remotely via Zoom.

Please feel free to forward this announcement to colleagues who may be interested.

We wish everyone a happy and restful holiday break.

Best regards,

Lisa, Pedro & Vishvas

NPC Coordinators

 Fermilab**NPC****Neutrino Physics Center**

Conclusions

Conclusion

- The **door has closed on vanilla 3+1 light sterile neutrino solutions to the Short-Baseline Anomalies**. Full SBN program will be capable of extending this to wide variety of extended oscillating models
- However, **the anomalies themselves remain unexplained!**

Conclusion

LSND Anomaly
Decay-at-rest

MiniBooNE Anomaly
Decay-in-flight

Gallium Anomaly
Radioactive Source

Directly probed by upcoming JSNS²/JSNS²-II results

	Protons	Zero Proton

Very difficult to explain ~20% effect with BSM physics.

Backup Slides

MicroBooNE Photon Backup

Predicted Backgrounds

1. Introduction

MicroBooNE...

..and MiniBooNE

What we know

2. The Dark Sector

Minimal Portals

Dark Neutrinos

Our e^+e^- Signal

3. e^+e^- Selection

Reject Background

Key Observables

- **Total Event Rate**
 - Background rate: 76.4 ± 25.0

Background Events	
NC $1\pi^0$	42.3
Out of TPC	11.8
CC $1\pi^0$	6.9
Other	10.2

Expect **71.2 neutrino induced backgrounds** of which **78% contain at least one π^0**

Predicted Systematic Uncertainty

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Key Observables

- **Total Event Rate**
 - Background rate: 76.4 ± 25.0

Cross-Section uncertainties on **NC π^0 production** dominate the systematic uncertainties on total background.

Highlights the **importance of the constraining sidebands**

Uncertainty Breakdown	
Cross-Section	24.2%
Detector	19.9%
Flux	8.0%
MC Statistic	5.5%
Geant4	1.2%

Total uncertainty 32.8%

NC $1\pi^0$ Constraining Sidebands

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Key Observables

Constraints

Two high statistics two-shower samples to constrain the cross-section systematics of our primary background, NC $1\pi^0$.

NC $1 \pi^0$ Constraining Sidebands

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..and MiniBooNE

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Constraints

Two high statistics two-shower samples to **constrain the cross-section systematics of our primary background, NC $1 \pi^0$.**

Same samples have been used for this purpose in MicroBooNE's NC Δ radiative and coherent single-photon searches, as well as the **first sub GeV measurement of NC $1 \pi^0$ cross-section on Argon**

MicroBooNE Collaboration [Phys.Rev.D 107 \(2023\) 1, 012004](https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.01200)

Effect of Constraints

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Constraints

76.4 backgrounds (majority NC π^0 !)

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76.4 backgrounds (majority NC π^0 !)

Measure and constrain them!

Effect of Constraints

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Constraints

Effect of constraint is a

- **9% reduction in expected background events,**
- **27% reduction in the relative systematic uncertainty (32.8%→24.9%)**

Unconstrained Background: 76.4 ± 25.0 (32.8%)

Constrained Background: 69.7 ± 17.3 (24.9%)

Effect of Constraints: Observables

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Unconstrained Background: 76.4 ± 25.0 (32.8%)

Constrained Background: 69.7 ± 17.3 (24.9%)

} 1 Bin Total event Rate

- Overall effect of constraint on both background prediction and systematic uncertainty is consistent when constraining in our key observable distributions

Electrons or Photons?

1. Introduction
MicroBooNE...
..and MiniBooNE

Strong
Electron ↔ photon
separation

Photons deposit twice as much energy per unit length at shower start
(Shower dE/dx)

Aux Materials

Overall Kinematic Agreement

MiniBoONE

Shower/Visible Energy

Excess

Shower/Visible Angle

MicroBoONE

Shower Energy vs Angle - Excess Events

- **Further exclusive BSM e^+e^-/γ studies**

- Analysis shown today is a **very forward selection**, due to targeted signal phase space and rejection of out-of-TPC backgrounds
- **Further work needed to see applicability to other analysis**

Testing Meson Portal Dark Sector Solutions to the MiniBooNE Anomaly at CCM [arXiv:2309.02599]

MicroBooNE Single-Photon/ e^+e^- Landscape – Stitching Together

1. Introduction
MicroBooNE...
..and MiniBooNE
What we know

2. The Dark Sector
Minimal Portals
Dark Neutrinos
Our e^+e^- Signal

3. e^+e^- Selection
Reject Background
Key Observables
Constraints
Signal Efficiency
Sensitivities
Sidebands

4. Results
Key Observables
Exclusion Regions
 e^+e^- Conclusions

5. Summary
Overview

M. Ross-Lonergan
Feb 14th 2025 190

Inclusive γ

Anything that **looks** like a single-photon!

Δ Radiative γ

Coherent γ

Dark Neutrino e^+e^- Pairs

Exclusive searches:

Targeting *specific, true single-photons*/ true e^+e^-

All this are inclusive single-photon signals!

Rejection power pretty much **entirely due to $1\gamma 1p$**

Little or no sensitivity/separation power $1\gamma 0p$ channel

UpScattering can probe vast array of short-lifetime dark sector particles!

Traditional, Long-lived decay-in-flight HNL's have to both **survive to detector AND decay inside..**

Short-Lived Regime

Long Lived Regime
(Well probed in past experiments)

Heavy sterile neutrino ν_4
Charged under a **dark sector $U(1)'$**

- With its own gauge boson Z'

- **Neutrino Portal:** Mixing allows for ν_4 production in scattering
- **Vector Portal:** Allows for tiny coupling of Z' to e^+e^- pairs & quarks

MiniBooNE

FERMILAB-PUB-18-33
OSU-HEP-1

Dark Neutrino Portal to Explain MiniBooNE excess

Enrico Bertuzzo,^{1,*} Sudip Jana,^{2,3,†} Pedro A. N. Machado,^{3,‡} and Renata Zukanovich Funchal^{1,§}

Neutrino mode

Events/MeV

Reconstructed neutrino energy in MeV

Light Z' regime $m_{Z'} < m_4$

- $m_{Z'} : 30 \text{ MeV}, m_4 : 420 \text{ MeV}$

Decays via two, 2-bodys decays with an **on-shell Z'**

$U(1)'$ mediated decays of heavy sterile neutrinos in MiniBooNE

Peter Ballett,^{1,*} Silvia Pascoli,^{1,†} and Mark Ross-Lonergan^{2,‡}

Excess Events

Reconstructed Visible Energy [GeV]

- MiniBooNE excess data
12.84e20 POT Neutrino-Mode
- This Model
 $M_{Z'} = 1.25 \text{ GeV}, M_N = 0.140 \text{ GeV}$
- Sterile Neutrino Oscillation
 $\sin^2 2\theta = 0.894, \Delta m^2 = 0.04 \text{ eV}^2$

Heavy Z' regime $m_{Z'} > m_4$

- $m_{Z'} : 1,250 \text{ MeV}, m_4 : 140 \text{ MeV}$

Decay via **off-shell Z'** through 3-body kinematics.

Phase Space of Interest for MiniBooNE

Fermilab

Protons

ν_μ

ν_4

ν_μ

MicroBooNE

Both critical!

Phase Space of Interest for MiniBooNE

MicroBooNE

3+1 Backup

$\bar{\nu}_e$ Disappearance

b

Δm_{41}^2 (eV^2)

Figure 16: MicroBooNE 95% CL_s sensitivity and data exclusion curves for ν_μ disappearance-only. The solid black curve represents the exclusion contour. The blue dashed curve represents the sensitivity contour. Seven channels are used in the oscillation fit while only the ν_μ disappearance oscillation effect is considered. The frequentist CLs sensitivity curve corresponds to the median value for each Δm_{41}^2 and the green/yellow bands correspond to 68.3% (1σ) and 95.5% (2σ) confidence levels.

Base Cross section model: GENIE v3.0.6
Tune to T2K $\nu_\mu CC0\pi$ cross section

Sideband channels : ν_μ

ν_μ channels constrain ν_e prediction \rightarrow universality of cross section modeling for CC interactions and common hadron parentage

ν_e CC
 $\chi^2 = 14.95/25$

Will constrain ν_e

ν_μ CC
 $\chi^2 = 9.32/25$

ν_e CC
 $\chi^2 = 23.41/25$

Will constrain ν_e

ν_μ CC
 $\chi^2 = 24.28/25$

Constrained ν_e channels

ν_e CC
constrained by all non- ν_e channels

Without
Constraint:
 $\chi^2 = 37.91/50$

With Constraint:
 $\chi^2 = 41.62/50$

H.Weï & S. Martynenko

Two Beam ν_e Appearance Data Exclusion

Appearance channel influenced more by BNB (4x less ν_e and 2x more ν_μ than NuMI)

BNB ν_e data has deficit \rightarrow boosts the ν_e appearance limits (smaller appearance angle $\theta_{\mu e}$)

BNB
(NuMI ~similar)

Pandora Nue BNB

WireCell Nue BNB

Degeneracy Breaking using Two Beams

H. Wei & S. Martynenko

Degeneracy Breaking using Two Beams

H.Wei & S. Martynenko

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Degeneracy Breaking using Two Beams

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Degeneracy Breaking using Two Beams

H. Wei & S. Martynenko

Reconstruction pipeline

JINST 12 P08003 (2017)
 JINST 13 P07006 (2018)
 JINST 13 P07007 (2018)
 JINST 13 P05032 (2018)
 JINST 16 P06043 (2021)

Phys. Rev. Applied 15
 064071 (2021)
 Wire-Cell PatRec Paper
<https://github.com/WireCell/wire-cell-toolkit>

Reconstruction for the analysis is performed via **Wire-Cell** package:

Noise Filtering
 Signal Processing

3D imaging
 Clustering
 Charge-Light matching

3D trajectory &
 dQ/dx fitting
 Cosmic muon tagger

Multi track fitting
 3D vertexing
 Particle identification

Proton or No Proton?

- Crucial to this search the ability to tell **true zero-proton events** like a coherent scattering (or a BSM decay) from neutrino scattering with hadronic activity

Vs Any other neutrino induced backgrounds

Vs

Two single-photon candidate events. Nice well reconstructed showers with consistent dE/dx fo a photon

Zooming out gives a clearer picture and highlights difficulty of $1\gamma 0p$ events:
We don't know where the neutrino interaction vertex took place

Along the projected path the photon would have traveled in one case we see a short, stubby deposit of charge, a missed low-energy proton

Zooming out gives a clearer picture and highlights difficulty of $1\gamma 0p$ events:
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The PSV: Proton Stub Veto

The PSV is a BDT trained to search for any evidence of missed hadronic activity that would be evidence of an incoherent scattering

PSV vetoes 70%
of protons down
to **~10 MeV KE**

**~50 KeV typical
threshold** for pandora
track reconstruction

'It's easier to veto than reconstruct..'

The PSV: Proton Stub Veto

The PSV is a BDT trained to search for any evidence of missed hadronic activity that would be evidence of an incoherent scattering

"Demonstration of new MeV-scale capabilities in large neutrino LArTPCs using ambient radiogenic and cosmogenic activity in MicroBooNE"

Phys. Rev. D 111, 032005 (2025)

MicroBooNE Phys. Rev. D 109, 052007 (2024)

Detection of Dark Sector Particles: Scattering

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3 ν Paradigm
How we got here

2. [Short-Baselines](#)
Anomalies
Sterile Neutrinos

3. [Where We Stand](#)
 $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ Results
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 ν_e Disappearance
 ν_μ Disappearance
 ν_μ Cosmology
New Ideas

4. [The Dark Sector](#)
Minimal Portals
Accelerator Probes

ν Neutrino Portal

N_{HNL}

Neutrino Detector

ν_μ

π^0

ϕ Scalar Portal

ϕ_{HPS}

μ^+

μ^-

γ Vector Portal

A^{Dark}

$\bar{\chi}$

χ

χ

A^{Dark}

A^{Dark}

e^+

e^-

This dark matter candidate, χ , is stable but enters the detector and **scatters** off an atom, so-called trident e^+e^- production

Powerful Dark Sector Probes: not just neutrino portals

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ICARUS collaboration
arXiv:2411.02727 [hep-ex] 2024

MicroBooNE Collaboration
arXiv:2501.08052 [hep-ex] 2025

MicroBooNE Collaboration
Phys. Rev. Lett. 132, 241801 2024

MicroBooNE collaboration
Phys. Rev. Lett. 132, 041801 2024

e^+e^- Signal Efficiencies

Not a fair apple-to-apple comparison, however worth comparing to past results

1. Introduction

MicroBooNE...

..and MiniBooNE

What we know

2. The Dark Sector

Minimal Portals

Dark Neutrinos

Our e^+e^- Signal

Reject Background

Key Observables

Constraints

@ **200 MeV** This result: **~15%** VS

4%: 1st gen NC Δ Radiative
Single-Photon Phys. Rev. Lett. 128, 111801 (2022)

Almost Ready to Unblind... some more sidebands

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Our e+e- Signal

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Signal Efficiency

Sensitivities

Sidebands unblinded and validated (no signal expected in these samples)

Sideband designed to check
single-shower NC π^0
backgrounds agreement

Sideband designed to validate our
simulation of neutrino events
originating outside our TPC
(Out-of-TPC or "Dirt" backgrounds)

The world's first direct limits on these dark sector models and, at the 95% confidence level, **excludes the majority of the parameter space viable as a solution to the MiniBooNE anomaly** (especially for light Z' boson masses)

$$\frac{|E^{e^+} - E^{e^-}|}{E^{e^+} + E^{e^-}}$$

Towards "Background Free" Dark Sector Searches

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5. Future
 Towards Bkg Free

Nano Second
Timing

Angular
Resolution

For overlapping e+e- angular resolution still plays a huge role.

Towards "Background Free" Dark Sector Searches

Nano Second
Timing

Angular
Resolution

Vertex & MeV
Scale Activity

BSM Decay

Neutrino Scattering

Not just decays, any *coherent* scattering

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Towards "Background Free" Dark Sector Searches

Nano Second Timing

Angular Resolution

Vertex & MeV Scale Activity

Rejecting events with low energy proton "blips" below 20 MeV at ~60% efficiency

"First Search for Neutral Current Coherent Single-Photon Production in MicroBooNE"
MicroBooNE, arXiv:2502.06091 [hep-ex]

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- (1) NC π^0 events where one daughter photon was low energy and not reconstructed
- (2) π^0 events from neutrino interactions **outside of the TPC** whose daughter photons scatter inside
- (3) NC π^0 from neutrino interactions **inside of the TPC** where **one daughter photon leaves detector** before pair converting

Fiducialize?

You never more than **116 cm** from TPC boundary

- (1) NC π^0 events where one daughter photon was low energy and not reconstructed
- (2) π^0 events from neutrino interactions **outside of the TPC** whose daughter photons scatter inside
- (3) NC π^0 from neutrino interactions **inside of the TPC** where **one daughter photon leaves detector** before pair converting

Average distance to TPC boundary is **38 cm** (less than 2λ)

Dark Sector searches with Accelerator Neutrinos

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- Minimal Portals

Natural place to search

1. Impressive **increase in neutrino beam intensity** over past decades

From **240 kW (2013)** to successful **1.018 MW (2024)** tests in just over a decade

Dark Sector searches with Accelerator Neutrinos

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Accelerator Probes

Natural place to search

1. Impressive **increase in neutrino beam intensity** over past decades

DUNE (Phase 1) to start with a **1.2MW beam** with upgrade paths for Phase II including

- **ACE-MIRT** (Main Injector Ramp and Targetry upgrade): Beam power to **2.0MW**
- **ACE-BR** (Booster Replacement): Beam power to **2.4MW**

Parameter	PIP-II Booster	ICD-2	BSR v1	BSR v2
Linac Energy	0.8 GeV	2 GeV	2 GeV	
Minimum Linac Current	2 mA	2 mA	2 mA	5 mA
GeV-scale Accumulator Ring	Optional	Optional	Required	Optional
RCS Energy	8 GeV	8 GeV	8 GeV	
RCS Intensity	6.5 e12	26 e12	37 e12	
RCS Circumference	474.2 m	553.2 m	570 m	
RCS Rep. Rate	20 Hz	10 Hz	20 Hz	
Number of Batches	12	6	5	
Accumulation Technique	Slip-stacking	Conventional	Conventional	
8 GeV Accumulation	Recycler	Recycler	Main Injector	
Available RCS Power	80 kW	170 kW	750 kW	
Main Injector Intensity	80 e12	156 e12	185 e12	
Main Injector Cycle Time	1.2 s	1.2 s	1.4 s	
Main Injector Power (120 GeV)	1.2 MW	2.4 MW	2.4 MW	
Upgraded Main Injector Power		3.3 MW	4.0 MW	

Further upgrade paths as high as **4.0MW** have been investigated

R. Ainsworth et al. [An Upgrade Path for the Fermilab Accelerator Complex](#)

J. Eldred et al. [Design Considerations for Fermilab Multi-MW Proton Facility in the DUNE/LBNF era](#)

Reactor (RAA) Global Anomaly?

We have several valid models of reactor fluxes that **have no anomaly**.

C. Giunti et al Physics Letters B Volume 829, 10 June 2022, 137054

In fact, **global fits of reactors** essentially exclude the BEST and Neutrino-4 allowed regions. E.g the **Estienne-Fallot (EF) reactor flux** model

$$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$$

Positive Hints

- Gallium
- Neutrino 4

Null Results

- DANSS
- NEOS+RENO
- STEREO
- PROSPECT-I
- KATRIN
- Global Reactors?

- BEST **was** the new testing ground for this decades old anomaly
- BEST result is **extremely compelling**, the **anomaly is confirmed** but sterile origin is NOT confirmed
- ***Might be the most robust neutrino anomaly right now***

Lots of scrutiny: E.g. A larger value of the half-life of ^{71}Ge used to compute the neutrino cross sections on ^{71}Ga could explain the difference

E.B Norman et al, [PhysRevC.109.055501 \(2024\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.05501)

“With this experiment, the potential explanation of the Gallium Anomaly being due to an unexpectedly long ^{71}Ge half-life has been ruled out, leaving the anomaly’s origin as an open question”

What do e^+e^- look like in LArTPCs?

Indistinguishable
from photons

What do e^+e^- look like in LArTPCs?

Indistinguishable
from photons

Don't just look like single-photons